

Potential Markers of Consciousness in Other Animals:

Key References

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Animal consciousness research has so far focussed on five broad types of potential marker of consciousness in other animals: learning-related tests, integrative decision-making, mental simulation, metacognitive and report-like behaviour, and REM-like sleep and dream-like states. This document provides some key references regarding each type of test followed by a summary table.

1. Learning-related tests

Goal-directed learning (inc. one-shot re-evaluation of rewards/punishers)

Balleine, B.W. & Dezfouli, A. (2019). Hierarchical action control: Adaptive collaboration between actions and habits. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 02735. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02735>

Balleine, B.W. & Dickinson, A. (1998). Goal directed instrumental action: Contingency and incentive learning and their cortical substrates. *Neuropharmacology*, 37, 407-419. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0028-3908\(98\)00033-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0028-3908(98)00033-1)

Dickinson, A. & Balleine, B. (1994). Motivational control of goal-directed action. *Animal Learning and Behavior*, 22(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03199951>

Robinson, M.J. & Berridge, K.C. (2013). Instant transformation of learned repulsion into motivational "wanting". *Current Biology*, 23, 282-289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.01.016>

Trace conditioning

Droege, P., Weiss, D.J., Schwob, N. & Braithwaite, V. (2021). Trace conditioning as a test for animal consciousness: a new approach. *Animal Cognition*, 24(6), 1299-1304. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-021-01522-3>

Grover, D., Chen, J. Y., Xie, J., Li, J., Changeux, J. P., & Greenspan, R. J. (2022). Differential mechanisms underlie trace and delay conditioning in *Drosophila*. *Nature*, 603(7900), 302–308. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04433-6>

Knight, D.C., Nguyen, H.T. & Bandettini, P.A. (2006). The role of awareness in delay and trace fear conditioning in humans. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience*, 6, 157–162. <https://doi.org/10.3758/CABN.6.2.157> (Substantiating tentative link to consciousness in humans.)

Paoli, M., Macri, C. & Giurfa, M. (2023). A cognitive account of trace conditioning in insects. *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, 57, 101034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2023.101034>

Solomon, P.R. Vanderschaaf, E.R., Thompson, R.F. & Weisz, D.J. (1986). Trace conditioning of the rabbit's classically-conditioned nictitating-membrane response. *Behavioral Neuroscience*, 100(5), 729-744. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0735-7044.100.5.729>

Woodruff-Pak, D.S. & Disterhoft, J.F. (2008). Where's the trace in trace conditioning? *Trends in Neurosciences*, 31(2), 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2007.11.006>

Second-order conditioning

Birch, J., Ginsburg, S. & Jablonka, E. Unlimited Associative Learning and the origins of consciousness: a primer and some predictions. *Biol Philos* 35, 56 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10539-020-09772-0> (Discussion of relevance to consciousness in the context of the Unlimited Associative Learning framework.)

Farr, E. J., & Savage, G. E. (1978). First- and second-order conditioning in goldfish and their relation to the telencephalon. *Behavioral Biology*, 22, 50–59. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0091-6773\(78\)92004-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0091-6773(78)92004-7)

Gewirtz, J. C., & Davis, M. (2000). Using Pavlovian higher-order conditioning paradigms to investigate the neural substrates of emotional learning and memory. *Learning & Memory*, 7, 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.1101/lm.35200>

Learning about incongruent cues

Ben-Haim, M. S., Dal Monte, O., Fagan, N. A., Dunham, Y., Hassin, R. R., Chang, S. W. C., & Santos, L. R. (2021). Disentangling perceptual awareness from nonconscious processing in rhesus monkeys (*Macaca mulatta*). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*, *118*(15), e2017543118.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2017543118>

Learning from cross-modal cues (e.g. a combination of a particular visual stimulus and a particular odour)

Gnaedinger, A., Gurden, H., Gourévitch, B. et al. (2019). Multisensory learning between odor and sound enhances beta oscillations. *Scientific Reports*, *9*, 11236 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47503-y>

Palmer, T. D., & Ramsey, A. K. (2012). The function of consciousness in multisensory integration. *Cognition*, *125*(3), 353–364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2012.08.003> (Substantiating tentative link to consciousness in humans)

Okray, Z., Jacob, P.F., Stern, C. et al. (2023). Multisensory learning binds neurons into a cross-modal memory engram. *Nature*, *617*, 777–784 (2023).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06013-8>

Reversal learning

Bublitz, A., Weinhold, S. R., Strobel, S., Dehnhardt, G., & Hanke, F. D. (2017). Reconsideration of serial visual reversal learning in octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*) from a methodological perspective. *Frontiers in Physiology*, *8*, 54.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2017.00054>

Mota, T., & Giurfa, M. (2010). Multiple reversal olfactory learning in honeybees. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, *4*, 48.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2010.00048>

Strang, C. G., & Sherry, D. F. (2014). Serial reversal learning in bumblebees (*Bombus impatiens*). *Animal Cognition*, *17*, 723–734.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-013-0704-1>

Travers, E., Frith, C. D., & Shea, N. (2018). Learning rapidly about the relevance of visual cues requires conscious awareness. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 71, 1698–1713. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17470218.2017.1373834>
(Substantiating tentative link to consciousness in humans)

2. Integrative Decision-Making

i.e. integrating multiple sources of information in decision-making, including exteroceptive, interoceptive, and affective (including nociceptive & valence) information.

Conditioned place preference and aversion

Adcock, S.J.J. & Tucker, C. B. (2020). Conditioned place preference reveals ongoing pain in calves 3 weeks after disbudding. *Scientific Reports*, 10, 3849. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-60260-7>

Paul, E.S., Edgar, J.L., Caplen, G. & Nicol, C.J. (2018). Examining affective structure in chickens: valence, intensity, persistence and generalization measured using a Conditioned Place Preference test. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 207, 39-48. <https://doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.applanim.2018.07.007>

Sufka, K.J. (1994). Conditioned place preference paradigm: A novel approach for analgesic drug assessment against chronic pain. *Pain*, 58(3), 355-366. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3959\(94\)90130-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3959(94)90130-9)

Wang, J., Wu, X., Li, C., Wei, J., Jiang, H., Liu, C. et al (2012). Effect of morphine on conditioned place preference in rhesus macaques. *Addiction Biology*, 17, 539-546. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1369-1600.2010.00289.x>

Motivational tradeoffs

Adcock, S.J.J. & Tucker, C.B. (2021). Injury alters motivational trade-offs in calves during the healing period. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 6888. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-86313-z>

Cabanac, M. (1992). Pleasure: the common currency. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 155, 173-200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5193\(05\)80594-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5193(05)80594-6)

Cooper, J., Mason, G. & Raj, M. (1998). Determination of the aversion of farmed mink (*Mustela vison*) to carbon dioxide. *Veterinary Record*, 143, 359-361.

<https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.143.13.359>

Niel, L. & Weary, D.M. (2007). Rats avoid exposure to carbon dioxide and argon. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 107, 100-109.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2006.08.002>

Self-administration of pain relief

Colpaert, F.C., deWitte, P., Mondt, A.N., Awouters, F., Niemegeers, C.J.E., & Jansen, P.A.J. (1980). Self-administration of the analgesic suprofen in arthritic rats: evidence of *Mycobacterium butyricum*-induced arthritis as an experimental model of chronic pain. *Life Sciences*, 27, 921-928.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3205\(80\)90101-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-3205(80)90101-0)

Groening, J., Venini, D. & Srinivasan, V. (2017). In search of evidence for the experience of pain in honeybees: A self-administration study. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 45825. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep45825>

Sneddon, L.U. (2003). The evidence for pain in fish: The use of morphine as an analgesic. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 83(2), 153-162.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(03\)00113-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(03)00113-8)

Judgement bias

Bateson, M., Desire, S., Gartside, S.E. & Wright, G.A. (2011). Agitated honeybees exhibit pessimistic cognitive biases. *Current Biology*, 21, 1070-1073.

<https://doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.cub.2011.05.017>

Deakin, A., Browne, W.J., Hodge, J.J.L., Paul, E.S. & Mendl, M. (2016). A screen-peck task for investigating cognitive bias in laying hens. *PLoS ONE*, 11(7), 20158222. <https://doi.org/10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0158222>

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Lecorps, B., Weary, D.M. & von Keyserlingk, M.A.G.G. (2018). Pessimism and fearfulness in dairy calves. *Scientific Reports*, 8, 1421.

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Mendl, M., Burman, O.H.P., Parker, R.M.A. & Paul, E.S. (2009). Cognitive bias as an indicator of animal emotion and welfare: Emerging evidence and underlying mechanisms. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 118(3-4), 161-181.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2009.02.023>

Brain areas integrating valence, interoceptive, and exteroceptive information in service of flexible decision-making

Barron, A. B., & Klein, C. (2016). What insects can tell us about the origins of consciousness. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 113(18), 4900–4908. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1520084113>

3. Mental simulation

i.e. evidence suggestive of forms of mental simulation, including episodic memory: note that some tests require validation as measures of mental simulation, not just of consciousness.

Vicarious trial and error

Hu, D. & Amsel, A. (1995). A simple test of the vicarious trial and error hypothesis of hippocampal function. *Proceedings of the National Academy USA*, 92(12), 5506-5509. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.92.12.5506>

Redish, A.D. (2016). Vicarious trial and error. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 17, 147-159. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn.2015.30>

Taylor, J.G. & Reichlin, B. (1951). Vicarious trial and error. *Psychological Review*, 58(6),389-402. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0055482>

Tolman, E.C. (1939). Prediction of vicarious trial and error by means of the schematic sowbug. *Psychological Review*, 46, 318-336.

<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0057054>

Evidence suggesting episodic memory and episodic future thinking

Clayton, N.S. & Dickinson, A. (1998). Episodic-like memory during cache recovery by scrub jays. *Nature*, 395, 272-274. <https://doi.org/10.1038/26216>

Davies, J., & Clayton, N. (2024). *Is episodic-like memory like episodic memory?*
<https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.107254>

Jozet-Alves, C., Bertin, M. & Clayton, N.S. (2013). Evidence of episodic-like memory in cuttlefish. *Current Biology*, 23(23), R1033-1035.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.10.021>

Liu, A. A., Henin, S., Abbaspoor, S., Bragin, A., Buffalo, E. A., Farrell, J. S., Foster, D. J., Frank, L. M., Gedankien, T., Gotman, J., Guidera, J. A., Hoffman, K. L., Jacobs, J., Kahana, M. J., Li, L., Liao, Z., Lin, J. J., Losonczy, A., Malach, R., ... Buzsáki, G. (2022). A consensus statement on detection of hippocampal sharp wave ripples and differentiation from other fast oscillations. *Nature Communications*, 13(1), 6000.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33536-x>

O'Brien, J., Sutherland, R.J. (2007). Evidence for episodic memory in a Pavlovian conditioning procedure in rats. *Hippocampus* 17, 1149-1152.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/hipo.20346>

Redshaw, J. and Bulley, A. (2018). Future-thinking in animals: capacities and limits. In Oettingen, G., Sevincer, A. T., & Gollwitzer, P.M (Eds.) *The Psychology of Thinking about the Future*. Guilford Press, pp. 31-51

Zentall, T.R., Clement, T.S., Bhatt, R.S. & Allen, J. (2001). Episodic-like memory in pigeons. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 8(4), 685-690.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/bf03196204>

4. Metacognitive and report-like behaviour

Post decision-wagering

Hampton, R.R. (2001). Rhesus monkeys know when they remember. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*, 98, 5359-5362.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.071600998>

Inman, A. & Shettleworth, S.J. (1999). Detecting metamemory in nonverbal subjects: A test with pigeons. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Animal Behavior Processes*, 25, 389-395. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0097-7403.25.3.389>

Smith, J.D., Shields, W.E., Allendoefer, K.R. & Washburn, D.A. (1998). Memory monitoring by animals and humans. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 127, 227-250. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0096-3445.127.3.227>

Smith, J.D., Strote, J., Egnor, R., Schull, J., McGee, K. & Erb, L. (1995). The uncertain response in the bottlenosed dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*). *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 124(4), 391-408.

<https://doi.org/10.1037//0096-3445.124.4.391>

Templer, V.L., Lee, K.A. & Preston, A.J. (2017). Rats know when they remember: transfer of metacognitive responding across odor-based delayed match to sample tests. *Animal Cognition*, 20, 891-906.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-017-1109-3>

Report-like protocols

Nieder, A., Wagener, L., & Rinnert, P. (2020). A neural correlate of sensory consciousness in a corvid bird. *Science*, 369(6511), 1626–1629.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb1447>

5. REM-like sleep & dream-like states

Eye movements suggestive of REM and/or other indicators or movements suggestive of dreaming (e.g. skin colouration changes)

Leung, L.C., Wand, G.X., Romain, M., Skariah, G., Kawakami, K., Deisseroth, K., Urbanm A.E. & Morrain, P. (2019). Neural signatures of sleep in zebrafish. *Nature*, 571, 198-204. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1336-7>

Pophale, A., Shimizu, K., Mano, T., Iglesias, T.L., Mertin, K., Hiroi, M., Asada, K., Garcia Andualus, P., van Dinh, T.T., Meshulam, L. & Reiter, S. (2023). Wake-like skin patterning and neural activity during octopus sleep. *Nature*, 619, 129-134.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06203-4>

Rößler, D., Kim, K., De Agrò, M., Jordan, A., Galizia, C.G. & Shamble, P.S. (2022). Regularly occurring bouts of retinal movements suggest an REM sleep-like state in jumping spiders. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*, 33, e2204754119.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2204754119>

Tainton-Haep, L.A.L., Kirszenblat, L.C., Notaras, E.T., Grabowska, M.J., Jeans, R., Feng, K., Shaw, P.J. & van Swindered, B. (2021). A paradoxical kind of sleep in *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Current Biology*, 31(3), 578-590.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2020.10.081>

Siegel, J.M. (2008). Do all animals sleep? *Trends in Neurosciences*, 31(4), 208-213.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2008.02.001>

Summary table

		Learning-related tests	Integrative Decision-Making	Mental Simulation	Metacognitive & report-like behaviour	REM-like sleep & dream-like states
(ADULT) NON-HUMAN ANIMALS	Monkeys	+	+	+	+	+
	Rodents	+	+	+	+	+
	Birds	+	+	+	+	+
	Insects	+	+	?	+?	+
	Teleost Fish	+	+	+	+?	+
	Decapod Crustaceans	+	+	?	?	+
	Cephalopods	+	+	+?	?	+
ALTERED STATES	Sedation	—	?	—	—	+
	Epileptic seizure	—	?	?	?	—
UNCLEAR CAPACITY FOR CONSCIOUSNESS	Disorders of consciousness	—	?	?	—	+
	Babies	?	—	?	—	+
	Fetuses	—	—	—	—	+
ARTIFICIAL SYSTEMS	Neural organoids	?	?	—	—	—
	Xenobots	?	?	?	—	—
	AI	?	?	?	?	—

Table 1: A table summarizing the applicability of various consciousness-relevant tests to various potentially conscious systems. Legend:

'+' : test can be administered to population (possibly with some modifications) ('+' does *not* imply a test has already been validated);

'—' : test is either inapplicable or not meaningfully interpretable for the population;

'?' : more development is needed;

'+?' : applicable but with unclear interpretation.

Each 'test' column corresponds to multiple tests, grouped for convenience according to sharing similar rationales for face validity.